

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter* (IRRN) request that contributors use the following guidelines and style:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N ha: not 60 kg ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotype of BPH in ...
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg ha at 2-week intervals: 7%. 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors: four varieties. But There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the *IRRN* should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source or genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common — not trade — names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in *IRRN* contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Occurrence of rare elements in rice plants

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Mass spectra (Ms-702 mass spectrograph) of the flag leaves of some rice varieties revealed the presence of the rare elements Cr, As, Br, Sr, Ag, Ba, and Pb as well as that of essential elements. We estimated the amount of such rare elements (see table). □

Estimated levels of rare elements in rice plants, Aduthurai, India

Element	Quantity (ppm) of element ^a			
	Ponni	Co 25	IR50	IR26
Cr51	53	52	54	54
As75	2	2	1	2
Br79	3	3	3	3
Sr88	12	14	14	15
Ag107	1	1	1	2
Ba138	1066	1017	1270	1437
Pb208	5	5	5	8

^a The values presented are on ash weight basis relative to silicon, used as an internal standard. Percent silicon is about 18%. The estimate of the volatile element As is approximate because of probable loss during ashing.

CN505-5-32-9, a photoperiod-sensitive semidwarf for rainfed lowlands

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CN505-5-32-9, a promising lowland rice, is from the cross IR26/SML 40-10-4. Selection from F₂ was made at the RRS, Chinsurah, as part of the rainfed lowland

breeding program. Different generations were evaluated for drought tolerance at early vegetative stage, waterlogging (50 cm deepwater), and pest resistance. Considering local yield trials in 1979, 1980, and 1981, in which CN505-5-32-9 averaged 5 t/ha, it was nominated for the 1982 kharif All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project deepwater trials and was evaluated at Tripura (West

Table 1. Yield performance of CN505-5-32-9 at different sites in India.

Site	Yield (t/ha)		Experimental mean (t/ha)	CD (0.05) (kg)	Max water depth ^a (cm)
	CN505-5-32-9	Tilakkachari (check)			
Arundhu tinagar (Tripura)	6.4	4.1	3.9	992	NA
Chinsurah (West Bengal)	5.8	4.3	4.1	654	40
Sindri (Bihar)	3.4	1.3	1.1	826	50
Pulla (Andhra Pradesh)	3.3	1.9	2.3	508	70
Patna (Bihar)	3.1	2.8	2.0	781	NA
Mean	4.4	2.9	2.7		

^a NA = not available.

Table 2. Height and duration of CN505-5-32-9 under different sowing and land situations at RRS Chinsurah (22.9°N, 88.4°E).

Sowing date	Culture	Land situation	Max water depth (cm)	Height (cm)	Days to flower
19 Mar 1982	Transplanted	Lowland	30	112	232
19 Mar	Transplanted	Medium land	5	102	235
30 Mar	Direct seeded	Lowland	40	135	215
31 Mar	Direct seeded	Upland	0	110	225
29 Apr	Transplanted	Lowland	45	113	190
2 Jun	Direct seeded	Lowland	70	138	160

Bengal), Bihar, and Andhra Pradesh. Mean grain yield over 5 locations was 4.4 t/ha and was more than that of check variety Tilakkachari (2.9 t/ha). At Arundhutinagar, it yielded around 6 t/ha. The water level varied from 40 to 70 cm in

the test locations (Table 1).

CN505-5-32-9 is photoperiod sensitive and flowers the first week of Nov when day length is 11 h 50 min. It has stiff culms and moderate elongation capacity, and is 110 cm tall when grown in shallow

water, but can elongate to 138 cm in deep water (Table 2).

CN505-5-32-9 produces 250 panicles/m² and long bold, white grains. The 1,000-grain weight is 24.8 g. It is resistant to bacterial leaf blight and brown spot. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Agronomic characteristics

Pant Dhan 4, a medium-maturing rice variety for irrigated lands

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Pant Dhan 4, a medium-maturing, dwarf (93 cm) rice variety was released recently in U. P. for cultivation in irrigated fields. It was developed in Sri Lanka from the cross IR262/Remadja and tested in the International Rice Observational Nursery as BG90-2 in 1974. The plants have good tillering capacity, mature in 126-132 d, and have high yield potential. Grains are long, slender, and translucent, with good cooking quality. It is moderately resistant to bacterial leaf blight and will be a good substitute for Jaya, which has become susceptible.

Pant Dhan 4 was tested in station trials from 1976 to 1980 and in state variety trials from 1979 to 1982 (see table). □

Performance of Pant Dhan 4 in state variety trials in Uttar Pradesh, India.

Trial centers	Grain yield (t/ha)		CD at 5%	CV in 5%	Days to maturity	
	Pant Dhan 4	Jaya			Pant Dhan 4	Jaya
<i>1981 kharif</i>						
Azamgarh	4.6	4.6	0.1	1.8	134	131
Bareilly	7.0	6.7	0.2	2.1	133	141
Haldwani	7.2	5.4	1.2	12.4	139	143
Hardoi	4.1	4.3	0.2	4.3	124	135
Mathura	5.1	4.8	0.3	4.5	123	130
Meerut	2.0	1.7	0.3	12.6	140	141
Jhansi	2.1	2.5	0.6	16.1	123	127
Barabanki	3.2	3.6	0.4	7.9	122	129
Etawah	3.1	4.3	1.0	20.6	122	126
Varanasi	3.1	3.5	1.5	12.0	110	126
Average	4.2	4.2	—	—	126	133
<i>1982 kharif</i>						
Azamgarh	3.8	4.5	0.09	1.73	131	133
Bareilly	5.9	5.6	0.07	0.75	132	139
Haldwani	5.8	5.5	0.9	9.8	152	154
Hardoi	4.8	4.7	0.3	5.3	130	138
Mathura	4.3	4.6	0.2	3.2	115	128
Meerut	6.3	4.5	1.0	10.8	139	139
Jhansi	5.6	4.7	N.S.	22.2	129	137
Barabanki	—	—	—	—	—	—
Etawah	—	—	—	—	—	—
Varanasi	—	—	—	—	—	—
Average	5.2	4.9	—	—	132	138

Variation of ripening periods among rice genotypes

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Most of the photosynthates accumulated as grain yield are formed from anthesis to senescence. Little information is available on the extent of variation in this duration. We sought to define ripening period for rice genotypes with a wide range of maturity duration. The entries were from

Vegetative and grain ripening periods in days for different rice types, Almora, India.

Duration	Genotypes (no.)	Duration (d)			
		Preanthesis		Postanthesis	
		Mean	Range	Mean	Range
Short	20	80	65-87	37	20-43
Medium	45	96	88-105	36	30-44
Medium-long	22	100	106-114	40	33-48
Long	4	120	115-125	37	28-45

different rice growing regions and included some local hill collections. Entries were transplanted in irrigated fields on 15

Jul 1981 and 1982 at Almora, at 1,600 m above sea level. Of an initial 100 entries, 9 were dropped because they did not